
17. Solar siblings

MOST STARS are believed to have been born in molecular clouds, as members of larger star clusters.

There are hints that our Sun was born in such a cluster, of perhaps a thousand other stars. The solar system's relatively sharp outer boundary, at about 30 au, suggests that the disk of gas and dust from which it formed was truncated by interactions with other cluster members.

Another clue is the large eccentricities and inclinations of the Kuiper belt objects. This suggests that a stellar encounter occurred early in the solar system's history, an event more likely in a denser stellar environment.

But was it, instead, born in isolation? If it was part of a larger cluster, where are the other members now?

ASTRONOMERS ARE searching for possible 'solar siblings', but also for 'solar twins' and 'solar analogues'.

Solar twins are defined as stars being essentially identical to the Sun in key all astrophysical parameters: mass, age, luminosity, chemical composition, temperature, surface gravity, magnetic field, and so on. Solar twins may be stars most likely to host planetary systems similar to our own, and may be best-suited to host life forms based on carbon chemistry and water oceans.

Solar analogues are more loosely defined, as stars that looked in the past, or will look in the future, very similar to the Sun. They can therefore provide a perspective of the Sun at some other point in its evolution.

A SYSTEMATIC SEARCH for solar twins started with the work of Hardorp (1978), who surveyed the near-ultraviolet spectra of 77 solar-type stars, but found no G2 dwarf stars matching the properties of the Sun.

From the late 1990s, searches used Hipparcos data to provide precise distances, and therefore accurate stellar luminosities, finding that HIP 79672 (18 Sco) and HIP 78399 are amongst the most promising solar twins.

Of stars with planets on the various Doppler planet-search programmes, only HD 186427 was found to have properties close to those of the Sun. Careful searches have nevertheless identified, in total, only around a dozen nearby stars as plausible solar twins.

IN CONTRAST to solar twins, which are defined as having largely identical spectra regardless of their origin, solar siblings do not need to be Sun-like in terms of their key properties, such as their effective temperature, mass, or luminosity. But if they formed at the same time as the Sun, and from the same gas cloud, they must have identical ages and chemical compositions.

The search for solar siblings also aims to gain a better understanding of the conditions under which life developed on Earth. Was this, for example, somehow related to whether the Sun was born in a cluster of other stars?

And this touches on the more controversial idea of 'panspermia', in which 'spores of life' are ejected and transmitted through space, protected within small rocky bodies on their travels. If the Sun was born in a cluster environment, solar siblings might be especially interesting targets in the search for life.

OF RELEVANCE to practical searches, solar siblings should share similar *Galactic kinematics* as the Sun. In other words, in the absence of some more energetic ejection from the birth cluster, they should be on similar orbits around the Galaxy as our Sun.

Given accurate space motions of the Sun and other nearby stars, and given a good model of the Galaxy's mass distribution (and hence gravitational potential), it should then be possible to 'reverse' their orbits, and calculate their original common birthplace.

The most optimistic estimates pre-Gaia have suggested that perhaps 10–60 still exist within 100 pc of the Sun (Valtonen et al. 2015). And while various solar siblings have been proposed in the past, with some of these subsequently contradicted by later work, no reasonably unambiguous candidates have been identified.

Martínez-Barbosa et al. (2016) concluded that our knowledge of the Galactic potential, e.g. concerning spiral arms and molecular clouds, is still too uncertain for the unambiguous identification of solar siblings based on astrometry and radial velocities alone. Accurate stellar ages and precise chemical abundances would be essential in making the searches more efficient.

TWO MAJOR EFFORTS have used the Gaia DR2 to advance the task of identifying possible solar sibling candidates. Both demonstrate how the problem of pinpointing possible candidates is strongly influenced by the quality of the astrometric data, by the uncertainty in the present knowledge of the mass distribution in the Galaxy (i.e. the Galactic potential), and perhaps even more so, by present inaccuracies in determining stellar abundances and, most acutely, stellar ages.

Adibekyan et al. (2018) used a database of 17 000 star spectra (AMBRE), and selected 55 with metallicities closest to the Sun's. Restrictions based on other chemical abundances resulted in 12 solar sibling candidates with chemistries very close to solar, and finally leaving just four candidates whose stellar ages are close to that of the Sun. For two of these, even the measured carbon isotope ratios are compatible with the solar value.

Given the difficulties of propagating the space velocities of these sibling candidates, and the Sun, backwards in time within the uncertainties of the Galactic potential, they simply used the Gaia astrometry

to calculate the position of their candidates in the so-called 'Toomre diagram'. As shown here, this represents each star's combined vertical and radial kinetic velocities as a function of their rotational velocity.

They concluded that HD 186302 is the most precisely characterised and the most probable of their candidates, in terms of its chemical composition, its age, and its orbital dynamics.

THE MORE RECENT study by Webb et al. (2020) further concentrated on the kinematical aspects of the search. Their starting sample was the SDSS–APOGEE DR14 catalogue, comprising more than 19 000 stars with high-quality spectra that have solar values of $[Fe/H]$ within their measurement uncertainties. Combining this with the Gaia DR2 astrometry provides the largest dataset of stars with measured abundances, as well as full three-dimensional positions and space velocities.

They started with a model star cluster within a static Galaxy containing a bulge, a disk, and a halo. They assume that it 'dissolves' quickly, so that escaping stars will have similar velocity distributions to models where the Sun was born in an unbound association, since most stars will then be unaffected by intra-cluster interactions. They then introduce subsequent time-dependent effects by adding either a rotating central bar, or a rotating central bar with two different types of spiral arms.

They then integrated the present Galactocentric position of the Sun backwards in time over 5 billion years, in each potential, to determine its location at birth. The model cluster is then initialised at this location, then the cluster itself is evolved forward again for 5 Gyr. Orbital 'actions' for each star are calculated all the way along these evolving orbits.

Without entering into the details of these procedures, all we need to know here is that the three orbital quantities referred to as 'actions' (J_R , L_Z , J_z) provide a powerful tool for characterising the orbits of stars in the Galaxy's gravitational potential, essentially describing the amount of oscillation of the star along its orbit in the Galactocentric directions (R , ϕ , z).

When these quantities are compared to the values for the Sun, they could pick out those stars which are closest to the Sun in terms of their orbital motions over the past 5 billion years.

Although their detailed conclusions are sensitive to the assumed details of the Milky Way's bar, spiral arms, and giant molecular cloud populations, they ended up with a list of just over 100 primary candidates, and they provide the values of the orbital actions that any true solar sibling is likely to possess. Interestingly, several of the candidates previously suggested by Martínez-Barbosa et al. (2016) also meet the orbital criteria estimated by Webb et al. (2020). And, in contrast with some previous work, they were able to exclude M67 as the Sun's birth cluster.

Their top candidate, Solar Sibling 1, lies at a distance of 360 ± 80 parsec. It has a dynamical history very close to that of the Sun, even in the absence of strong interactions with the bar, spiral arms, or giant molecular clouds.

GAIA, IT SEEMS, has allowed the discovery of the first of our Sun's birth cluster siblings. Presumably others will soon be found. And I imagine that this new field of study will develop in a variety of interesting ways.

